

EFFECT OF EXTREME ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS ON BEHAVIOR OF EARTH CEMENT BLOCKS WITH AND WITHOUT FIBRE REINFORCEMENT

Y. Yogananth^{a*}, P. Sangeeth^a and N. Sathiparan^a

^a Department of Civil Engineering, University of Jaffna.

* yogananth10jan@gmail.com

Graphical Abstract

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1. Introduction

Masonry buildings are affected by weathering processes due to environmental, anthropic, and physical causes. Among the environmental causes, attacks due to acid, salt, chlorate and alkaline play a significant role. Rising damp and other chemical attacks are prevented by the insertion of damp-proof courses or chemical proofing in modern constructions. However, houses in rural areas were constructed without these, and there are usually damp problems at the wall bases and chemical attack from the environment.

Fibre reinforced soil block is meant as a technique to improve the engineering characteristics of the soil blocks. In nowadays, synthetic fibre shows the better performance than natural fibre. But, consider the environmental issues, natural fibre are most preferable. The coconut fibre, sisal fibre, hemp, palm, jute, flax, straw, bamboo and cane fibre are commonly used fibre based on availability (Danso et al., 2015).

Although synthetic fibre reinforced soil blocks are showing better mechanical and durability performance than natural fibre reinforced blocks, there is interest on the application of natural fibre in blocks due to environmental concerns (Mahdi et al., 2012). Fibre reinforced soil block reduces maintenance problems of the adobe walls of rural houses due to weather ability problems. Published literatures show the addition of natural fibre decrease the dry density and increase the compressive strength and ductility with increase in fibre fractions. Although a considerable amount of work has been done in the area of fibre reinforcement, however, most of the work has been performed on concrete blocks and adobe. Still, study on fibre reinforcement on earth cement block (ECB) is limited.

This study is focused to contribute towards the effect of extreme environmental condition on the behavior of fibre reinforced stabilized earth blocks. This research mainly focused on the durability of earth cement blocks due to the extreme environmental conditions such as water, salt, acid, alkaline, wet-dry and freeze-thaw.

Table 1: Mix design of blocks

Block type	Cement: soil or sand volume ratio	Material used				
		Cement (kg)	Sand (kg)	Soil (kg)	Water (kg)	Fibre (g)
Earth cement blocks (ECB)	1:6	1	-	7.1	1.25	-
	1:8	1	-	9.45	1.4	-
	1:10	1	-	11.8	1.6	-
Cement sand blocks (CSB)	1:6	1	8.8	-	1.2	-
	1:8	1	11.7	-	1.3	-
	1:10	1	14.6	-	1.5	-
Fibre reinforced cement blocks	1:6	1	-	7.1	0.9	32.4

2. Methodology

Materials

Cement, soil, river sand, banana fibre and coconut coir were used for the preparation of blocks.

- Cement: Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) as described in Sri Lanka standard SS 855 (1999). Apparent density = 1362 kg/m^3 .
- Soil: The soil used in this investigation was sourced from Kilinochchi region located in northern Sri Lanka. Soil contained 45.8% of clay and silt, 50.2% of sand and 4% of gravel.
- Coconut coir: Locally available untreated coir, which average length is around 24 mm and diameter is around $20 \mu\text{m}$.
- Banana fibre: it is taken from waste products of banana cultivation. Fibre length is around 40 mm and diameter around $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Totally 306 soil blocks, 306 cement blocks and 192 fibre reinforced earth stabilized blocks were prepared according to the mix proportions as shown in Table 1. Blocks with the dimension of $100 \times 100 \times 60 \text{ mm}$ were prepared.

Tests

- Freeze and Thaw test: Freeze and thaw test was conducted according to the ASTM-D560 standard.
- Wet and Dry test: Wet- dry test was conducted according to the ASTM-D6611 standard (Liu et al., 2017).
- Water, salt, acid and alkaline resistance: Six specimens from each mix proportion were kept under different conditions for 28 days as follows: air, water, salt water, acid and alkaline.
- Compressive strength test: The compressive strength of the blocks was evaluated through universal axial compression testing machine

under displacement-controlled method, according to European standards (EN 1926, 1999).

3. Results

Compressive strength of soil blocks and sand blocks with the mix proportion of 1:6, 1:8, 1:10 was reduced for all the environmental condition. Soil blocks were shown higher strength than the river sand blocks in all of the conditions. Figure 1 (a) shows the strength reduction compared with different environment condition. Strength reduction in water and salt is less than 5% for both stabilized earth blocks and cement blocks. Alkaline strength reduction was 5-10% for both stabilized earth blocks and cement blocks. Strength reduction in acid was greater than 15% for stabilized earth blocks and 10-15% in cement sand blocks.

Wet-dry and freeze-thaw strength was reduced along the 3, 6, 9, 12 cycles in stabilized earth blocks and cement sand blocks. Wet-dry and freeze-thaw compressive strength was reduced with the mix proportion (1:6>1:8>1:10) in both stabilized earth blocks and cement sand blocks. Stabilized earth blocks were shown higher compressive strength in both conditions than the cement sand block in all occasions. Figure 1 (b) shows the strength reduction in freeze and thaw cycles. Strength reduction nearly 20% in stabilized earth blocks with the ratio of 1:8 and 1:10. But strength reduction was nearly 15% and 30% with respect to 1:8 and 1:10 for cement sand blocks. Figure 1(c) shows the strength reduction in wet and dry cycles. Wet-dry strength reduction nearly 50% in stabilized earth blocks and nearly 60% in cement sand blocks with the ratio of 1:8 and 1:10. Mix ratio of 1:6 blocks were shown the better strength compared with the ratio of 1:8 and 1:10 in both freeze –thaw and wet-dry condition.

Figure 1: Environmental effect on stabilized earth

Figure 2 shows the environmental effect on strength of unreinforced and fibre reinforced stabilized earth blocks. Fibre addition of blocks were shown the better strength reduction in acid and alkaline attack comparing with initial strength. But strength change was almost near value in water, environment and salt for reinforced and unreinforced blocks. Banana fibre was shown the slightly better strength reduction compared with the coconut fibre in acid and alkaline conditions. Fibre reinforced blocks were

shown the better compressive strength in most of the weathering conditions.

Figure 2: Environmental effect on unreinforced and reinforced blocks

4. Conclusion

The meaning of this experimental study was to evaluate the influence of fibre addition on the compressive strength of SEBs with different environmental conditions. According to the results, fibre reinforced blocks were shown better compressive strength in all the applied conditions. Comparatively, banana fibre reinforced blocks slightly better than the coconut coir blocks.

References

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